

ISSN 115 - 960X

Ilorin Journal of Business and Social Sciences

Volume 24, No 1

February, 2022

*Published by the Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, P.M.B. 1515, Ilorin, Nigeria*

ISSN 1115 – 960X

Ilorin Journal of Business and Social Sciences (IJBSS)

Volume 24, Number 1, February, 2022

PUBLISHED BY

THE FACULTY OF SOCIAL SCIENCES,
UNIVERSITY OF ILORIN,
P.M.B. 1515, ILORIN, NIGERIA.
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Contents	Pages
Effect of Currency Devaluation on Economic Growth in Nigeria: New Evidence From Dynamic OLS Dada, M. A. Olubiyi, E. A. Akinbode, S. O. Abalaba, B. P. Okungbowa, O. G.	1-19
Social Media Usage: The Poisoned Chalice Of Nigeria's Humanity Abiodun Adekunle Ogunola PhD	20-37
Conceptual Clarifications of Public Service Delivery, Public Policy, Public Administration and Governance In The Gambia Banna Sawaneh	38-53
Welfare Service Delivery For The Physically Challenged Elderly Persons in Kwara State Under The Economic Recession of Covid-19 Sunday Evaristus Abonyi Ph.D Charles Chukwujekwu Onwuka Ph.D	54-64
Value Creation and Customer Loyalty in The Nigerian Banking Sector: A Study of University Students in Ogun State, Nigeria ODUNLAMI, Samuel Abimbola, Ph.D SHONUBI, Akeem Olalekan, Ph.D	65-82
Influence of Retirement Planning on Retirement Satisfaction Among Retirees in Ilorin, Kwara State Abdussalam ABDULHAMEED Sunday Evaristus ABONYI Salamatu Abaji ABDULLAHI	83-100

Contents	Pages
The Nigerian Criminal Justice System: A Cursory Look at Salient Issues and Areas of Reform Habeeb Abdulrauf Salihu Monsurat Isiaka Obasanjo Solomon Balogun Tomisin Adedunmola Akangbe Abdullahi Kayode Ibrahim	101-117
Equity Issues in Employee Performance and Compensation: An Empirical Study of National Inland Waterways Authority (niwa), Lokoja, Nigeria. Tunde Anthony Puke Ph.D	118-135
Internally Displaced Persons and The 2019 General Elections in North Central Nigeria: A Study of Daudu Camp in Benue State Johnkennedy, Tersoo Ikyase Maigoge, E. S. Elyon Bala, Iranyang Shamaki	136-146
Defined Contribution Pension and Actuarial Expectation in Later Life For Active Employees Adeyele, J.S. (Ph.D.) Olujide, J.O. (Ph.D.) Ogunbenle, G.M. Jugu, Y.G. (Ph.D.) Jim-Suleiman, S.L. (Ph.D.) Ikeobi, N.R. (Ph.D.) Adamu, D.K. Angyak, J.A.	147-164
Historical Studies And Sustainable National Development In Nigeria Dr. Shehu Muhammad Danyaya	165-174

EFFECT OF CURRENCY DEVALUATION ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA: NEW EVIDENCE FROM DYNAMIC OLS

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Abstract

The extant literature is characterized with diverse views on policy impact prediction in respect of currency devaluation and economic growth. We have the optimists who view the policy impact prediction as positive due to its expansionary effect. We also have the pessimists who view it as negative due to its contractionary effect. There is ample evidence of this ambiguous relationship between currency devaluation and economic growth. The conclusion for different economies therefore is subject to empirical investigation. This study used dynamic OLS to examine the effects of currency devaluation as well as its associated returns on economic growth with special consideration to export and import of goods and services and inflation rate in Nigeria. Annual time series data covering the period 1981 to 2020 were fetched from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin augmented with latest version of WDIs of World Bank Group. The result shows that currency devaluation as well as its associated returns has a contractionary effect on output in support of the pessimist school of thought. Both inflation and export of goods and services have positively significant effect while import of goods and services has negatively significant effect on all the estimated models. The three control variables jointly produced the most desirable models with the highest adjusted R-square of about (0.998) in each case and with smallest variance of about (0.007, 0.003) respectively. The study, therefore, is concluded by recommending a substantial reduction in the naira-dollar exchange rate as well as import of goods and services while all measures should be taken in raising the volume of export of goods and services to accelerate economic growth in this so-called oil-rich nation.

Key words: Currency Devaluation, Naira-Dollar Exchange Rate, Dynamic OLS, Economic growth

JEL Classification Codes: *B22; E31; F13; F43; O47.*

Introduction

Currency devaluation is a reduction in the value of a nation's currency relative to that of other countries especially that of its trading partners. The rate at which one currency is exchanged for another currency in an international exchange market is called an exchange rate. For instance, Nigeria exchange rate against the United State Dollar is the amount of Naira that will be needed to exchange for one United State Dollar in the Naira-Dollar market. If more Naira is needed on a particular day to secure one United State Dollar, then we say Naira value has fallen relative to US dollar. On the other hand, if less Naira is needed to secure one US dollar in another day, we say the value of Naira has increased relative to US dollar. (See, Krugman., Obstfeld, & Melitz, 2012; Carbaugh, 2009; Radaelli, 1995; MacDonald, 2007; Salvatore, 2006; Klein & Shambaugh, 2010; Kallianiotis, 2013). It is very important to note that these rise and fall in the value of Naira have their own consequences on the economy, especially when the frequency of such a rise and fall is very high. Devaluation is a reduction in the value of a currency with respect to those goods, services or other monetary units with which that currency can be exchanged (Yioyio, 2015).

Currency devaluation has increasingly been used as a policy strategy to stimulate economic growth in many developing countries. Global institutions such as the Breton Wood financial institutions, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank (WB) have implicitly support currency devaluation as a strategic policy instrument to remedy balance of payment disequilibrium and output instability. See, Alexander (2020) as well as IMF(2019) on implications of currency depreciation on global financial stability. The main objective of currency devaluation is to accelerate external competitiveness and, thereby, improve the balance of payments position of a nation. This will likely produce the desired result of improvements in securing effective market competitiveness and consumption-switching toward domestic goods by making imported goods relatively more expensive. The more a country devalues its currency, the more expensive imported goods become. This is expected to reduce demand for imported goods and make locally produced alternatives attractive or open to consideration by the consumers who have developed a strong taste in favour of imported goods against locally produced goods for a very long time. This is in line with the traditional view in which currency devaluation policy is believed to produce an expansionary effect on aggregate demand for locally produced goods and output. (Edwards, 1985, Zelealem. 2006).

However, authors like (Cooper, 1971; Krugman & Taylor, 1978; Taylor, 1979, 1981; Agenor & Montiel (1996) held a contrary view by negating the validity of the benefits of devaluation in the context of developing countries. They argue that currency devaluation could harm domestic macroeconomic activity in the short run. This assertion is summarized and simplified in Obadan (2006) as the contractionary devaluation hypothesis.

The literature on currency devaluation and its effect on the economy has two diverse views in relation to devaluation-economic growth in developing countries, Nigeria inclusive. See Edwards, (1985), Zelealem(2006) as well as Cooper(1971), Krugman & Taylor(1978), Taylor(1979, 1981), Agenor & Montiel(1996). The optimist line of this debate suggests that devaluation policy will produce positive effect on growth while the pessimist alternative view suggests that devaluation will have adverse effect on growth. This controversy has thrown this topical issue open to further debate and find out from time to time which of these hypotheses would explain the real condition of a specific country as well as regions in less developed countries. Nigeria in the recent times has witnessed high volatile exchange rate and this has been worrisome to many stakeholders in the economy due to the effect this could have on economic growth and overall standard of living in the country.

This study therefore intends to examine empirically likely effect of the trend in exchange rate on the economy. Nigeria is located in West Africa. It is a member of ECOWAS and one of the sub-Saharan African countries. It is ranked 152 in the Human Development Index (HDI) of the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 2018). Nigeria is an oil-rich but import dependent nation with crude oil export as its mainstay of the economy. Thus, the economy is highly vulnerable to the volatility in the international oil market while its strength lies in the abundance of resources; both human and non-human including, liquid and solid minerals, favourable weather condition good agricultural land, its diversity as well as healthy, vibrant, agile and youthful population. Yet, she has her major weaknesses which include; weak socio-economic and political institutions, uncompetitive export, overdependence on crude oil as foreign exchange earner, mono-cultural economic nature, ethnic and religion diversities, security challenges especially in the recent time, ranging from Boko-haram insurgency, herdsmen-farmer clashes, kidnapping to pipe-line vandalization and many more. Just as evidenced by the current trend in security breakdown in different part of the country with high incidence of killings worsened by high level of corruption even among the so-called elites in charge of the nation.

These weaknesses are obvious reasons for its slow growth and continuous state of underdevelopment. Authors such as Todaro, (2011); Acemoglu & Robinson, (2006) among others have also emphasized that these weaknesses explain the poor economic growth being experienced as a country since its independence in 1960. Thus, policies such as currency devaluation in conjunction with building strong institutions, enhancing the efficiency of public sector, provision of necessary infrastructure to enhance productivity in the private sector, export promotion strategy, etc. have been used in the last two decades in order to stimulate economic growth. Currency devaluation therefore could be a strategy to make imported goods dearer in the local markets while exported goods are made cheaper and much more competitive in the international market. Mohammed, Agboola, Moshood & Abdullah (2015) observed that many developing countries have experienced currency crises especially in the last few decades leading to their contemplation on how beneficial or advantageous is

currency devaluation to their economies and the urge to charge for alternative economic and financial policy option.

Despite many studies on currency devaluation and its effect on the economy, the contributory role of variables such as import volume, export volume and inflation on currency devaluation effect on economic growth are either rarely emphasized or completely neglected. Most studies included net trade balance in their models without the interface of domestic prices. The use of dynamic ordinary least square (DOLS) is considered to be more appropriate and said to produce a more robust result especially when a group of integrated I(1) variables are found to be cointegrated. This paper examined the effect of currency devaluation on economic growth with simultaneous inclusion of import and export volume as well as consumer prices following a dynamic econometric procedure.

The remainder of this paper are organized as follows: Following this introductory section is section two which presents the literature review on devaluation-economic growth nexus, section three which describes the data and econometric methodology, section four which presents empirical results and section five which gives the concluding remarks.

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

There are two perspectives to the debate on the effect of currency devaluation on economic growth both theoretically and empirically. The first perspective is that devaluation impacts positively on economic growth. The second perspective is that devaluation impacts negatively on economic growth. See, (Edwards, 1985; Zelealem. 2006) as well as (Cooper, 1971; Krugman & Taylor, 1978; Taylor, 1979, 1981; Agenor & Montiel (1996) On the one hand, devaluation generates an expansionary effect via aggregate demand while on the other hand, through its effect on the cost of imported intermediate inputs, it produces a contractionary effect on the aggregate supply (Ilker, 1997). The likely effect of currency devaluation therefore will be the balance between its effects on aggregate demand as well as its effects on aggregate supply.

The basic motivation for the positive effect of currency devaluation is the Marshall–Lerner condition proposed by Alfred Marshall and Abba P. Lerner which refers to the condition that currency devaluation would only cause a balance of trade improvement if the absolute sum of the long-term export and import demand elasticity's is greater than unity. Traditional theorists suggest that devaluation has a positive effect on output while on the other hand, the monetarists are of the view that devaluation influences real magnitudes mainly through the real balance effect in the short-run, but leave all variables unchanged in the long-run.

The theoretical arguments in favour of the hypothesis of contractionary effect of currency devaluation are embedded both in terms of demand and supply-side channels through which exchange-rate fluctuation would influence economic activity. On the demand side, there are many reasons for considering currency devaluation is said to be

contractionary. First is by lowering aggregate demand via its adverse wealth effect to the extent of engendering an increase in the average price level, the real value of financial assets would fall, reducing household consumption expenditure. Second is by redistributing income from people with higher marginal propensity to consume (e.g. wage earners) to those with lower marginal propensity to consume (e.g. investors), leading to inadequacy in the aggregate demand. Third is that in the presence of external debt, devaluation would raise the debt service charge on a given stock of external debt denominated in foreign currency and would thereby decrease the level of real income from a given level of output. Fourth is that, under conditions of low import prices and exports elasticity's, devaluation would be contractionary in the short-run as it could worsen the trade deficit measured in domestic currency. This negates the Marshall-Lerner conditions which refer to the condition that currency devaluation would only cause a balance of trade improvement if the absolute sum of the long-term export and import demand elasticity's is greater than one. Through these and other expenditure-reducing mechanisms, devaluation is known to have an adverse effect on aggregate demand. This adverse effect is assumed to dominate the expansionary expenditure-switching effect that may arise from induced changes in relative prices. Contractionary effects of currency devaluation may also emanate from the supply side. Currency devaluation raises the cost of imported inputs as well as cost of production leading to a decrease in aggregate supply. In addition, currency devaluation may raise the domestic interest rate and wage level through an increase in the price level. This might also decrease aggregate supply in the economy (Kamal, Franklin & Rabindra, 2007).

Empirical Literature

A number of studies have provided some empirical information on devaluation-economic growth nexus across countries and regions. For instance, Khan (1988) investigated the experience of 67 developing countries with IMF programmes and concluded that they were successful in improving the current account, balance of payments, and in curbing inflation, but at the cost of a decline in the growth rate. The implication is that the concept of growth-oriented adjustments appears to be an irony if the programmes actually lead to low growth rates. This end-result of lowering growth rate of output is of great concern since economic growth is a substantial measure of the well-being of an economy.

Upadhyaya, Rainish, Kaushik and Bhandari (2013) examined the effect of currency devaluation on aggregate output using panel of countries in South-East Asia namely; Thailand, Malaysia, Indonesia and the Philippines from 1980 to 2010. The result of the error correction model shows that currency devaluation is contractionary in the short-run and the intermediate-run and that the noted contractionary effect comes from the change in nominal exchange rate and not from the change in foreign-to-domestic price ratio.

Morvillier (2019) employed GMM to determine how the level of currency undervaluation affects the growth-effect of inflation in a sample of 62 countries over

the period of 1980-2015. The result shows that higher currency undervaluation reinforces the contractionary growth-effect of inflation. Tarawalie (2010) determined the impact of real exchange rate on economic growth in Sierra-Leone. The result of the study revealed that real effective exchange rate correlated positively with economic growth in Sierra-Leone.

Osundina and Osundina (2013) investigated the effect of Naira depreciation on economic growth in Nigeria. The result of the analysis which is in line with the a priori expectation shows that devaluation reduces importation; encourages exportation and increases interest rate, inflation and unemployment are the side effects of currency devaluation in the short run. Ayen (2014) examined the effect of currency devaluation on output in Ethiopia using vector autoregressive modelling approach to analyse the quarterly time series data between 1998 and 2010. The result shows that currency devaluation has a contractionary effect in the long-run while the effect is neutral in the short-run.

Mohammed et al (2015), on the effects of currency devaluation on output growth in selected developing countries using fully modified OLS and error correction model for the panel data covering the period 1981 and 2010. The result of the study shows that there is no significant relationship in the short run while there is a negative relationship between currency devaluation and economic growth in the long-run. Razzaque, Bidisha and Khondker (2017) examined the relationship between exchange rate and economic growth in Bangladesh using the error correction modelling approach to analyse the time series data. The result shows that there is contractionary effect in the short-run while it is expansionary in the long-run. Adjei (2019) investigated the effect of exchange rate volatility on economic growth of Ghana between 1983 and 2010 using the autoregressive distributed lag approach. The result shows that exchange rate volatility have significant negative effect on economic growth both in the short and long-run.

Do (2019) examined the real exchange rate and economic growth nexus in Vietnam using time series data covering 2007-2017. Vector autoregressive estimation technique was adopted. The result shows that there exist a positive relationship between real exchange rate and economic growth. The forecast error variance decomposition (FEVD) result also suggests that the real effective exchange rate (REER) made only a small contribution to GDP growth over the period. Duran (2016) examined the local effect of exchange rate in Turkey over a period from 2004-2011 using the spatial-panel models, it was found that relatively less developed regions in Eastern parts of the country are positively affected from currency depreciations. Conrad and Jagessar (2018) investigated the impact of exchange rate movements as well as exchange rate misalignments on economic growth for the Trinidad and Tobago using time series data covering 1960 to 2016. The result shows that both exchange rate appreciation and misalignments have negative impact on economic growth.

Kenny (2019) investigated exchange rate management and economic growth for Nigeria between 1981 and 2015 using fully modified ordinary least square. The result shows that exchange rate, external reserve, money supply and capital input have significant impact on the economic growth of Nigeria; whereas labour shows no significant impact on economic growth in the long-run. Also, the dummy variable indicates a negative insignificant coefficient which suggests that fixed exchange rate wouldn't enhance the economy of Nigeria in the long run. Okoroafor and Adeniji (2017) investigated the response of currency devaluation and macroeconomic variables in Nigeria between 1986 and 2016. Adopting the vector error correction model (VECM) and impulse response function analysis, the result shows that exchange rate devaluation has a positive and significant relationship on macroeconomic variables tested, including economic growth in Nigeria. Nyasha and Tatenda (2019) investigated the impact of exchange rate on output and inflation in Zimbabwe using Johansen and vector error correction model, the result shows that fluctuations in real exchange rate are significant on real output and expansionary in both short-run and long-run. The study result also shows that exchange rate fluctuations are neither inflationary nor deflationary in the short-run, however, the devaluation of real exchange rate is found to be inflationary in the long-run.

There are other studies that have provided diverse empirical information on the impact of an increase in exchange rate of local to foreign currency (currency devaluation) on economic growth. They include Missio, Jayme, Britto, & Oreiro, (2015) for 63 developing countries, Tarawalie (2010) for Sierra-Leone, Di Nino, Eichengreen, & Sbracia, (2011) for Italy, Chen (2012) for 28 provinces in China, Aman, Ullah, Khan, & Khan, (2013) for Pakistan, Obansa, Okoroafor, Aluko, & Millicent (2013) for Nigeria, Habib, Mileva, & Stracca, (2017) for a panel of 150 countries, mixed sample data, Narayan (2007) for Fiji countries, Rodrik (2008) for panel of 188 countries. Those who found negative result in line with structural economics include Ribeiro, McCombie, & Lima, (2019) for sample of 54 developing countries, Ozcan (2020) for Turkey, Cottani, Domingo, & Shahbaz, (1990) for 24 cross-section of developing countries, Bahmani-Oskooee (2002) for five Asian countries.

Gap in Literature

Based on the available literature, the use of dynamic OLS to examine the effect of currency devaluation on economic growth is rare among the existing studies particularly country-specific studies that focused on Nigeria. Besides, the simultaneous inclusion of export, import and inflation as control variables to account for the role of export, import and inflation within a dynamic econometric environment is not a common trend in the existing body of literature, hence, this study used annual time series data for Nigeria between 1981 and 2020 to examine the effect of currency devaluation on economic growth by controlling export and import of goods and services as well as inflation rate.

Data and Methodology

The data for this study are purely time series data with yearly frequency. The starting year is 1981 while the end year is 2020. The variables for the study include official exchange rate, export and import of goods and services, consumer price index and gross domestic product (GDP). Data were sourced mainly from World Development Indicators (WDIs) of World Bank Group (WBG) and Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and Annual Reports of many years.

Model Specification

The model is based on the non-linear form of the simple Cobb-Douglas Production Function since the whole essence of this study is to capture the output effect of currency devaluation. Hanging on the framework of Mundell-Flemming model which concludes that currency devaluation is expansionary in terms of gross domestic product (GDP) due to the fact that it raises exports while lowering imports. The net effect will definitely be positive on the basis of this model prediction, hence, the study begins with a model of the form

$$Y = AL^{\beta_1} K^{\beta_2} \quad (1)$$

Where

Y represents the output level

L represents the labour input

K represents the capital input

A represents augmented technology

β_1 and β_2 are output elasticity with respect to labour and capital input

Exchange rate shows the strength of a nation's currency relative to other countries of the world. A strong currency implies a good economic status while a weak currency is a sign of bad economic status. However, a deliberate attempt to manipulate the value of a country's currency is usually done to achieve a particular objective. Any attempt to increase or decrease a country's exchange rate has important implication; for instance, an increased exchange rate raises the price of export and thereby lowering the demand for export in the foreign market while a decreased exchange rate lowers the price of export and thereby raising the demand for export in the foreign market. The domestic market is not left out in this scenario. For instance, an increased exchange rate will make import dearer and discourages demand for import in the domestic market while a decreased exchange rate will lower import prices and encourage demand for import. This kind of actions and reactions makes the whole drama interesting. It is no doubt that export and import as well as domestic prices affect aggregate output of a nation engaged in international trade.

Incorporating the currency devaluation variable as well other variables so mentioned into the production function yields

$$Y = AL^{\beta_1} K^{\beta_2} R^{\beta_3} X^{\beta_4} M^{\beta_5} V^{\beta_6} \quad (2)$$

Where

R represents naira-dollar exchange rate

X represents the export of goods and services

M represents the import of goods and services

V represents the consumer price index

$\beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$ and β_6 are output elasticity with respect to exchange rate, export, import and consumer prices

Transforming the non-linear multiplicative model into linear form, it becomes

$$\ln Y = \ln A + \beta_1 \ln L + \beta_2 \ln K + \beta_3 \ln R + \beta_4 \ln X + \beta_5 \ln M + \beta_6 \ln V \quad (3)$$

Note ' \ln ' represents natural logarithm of variables

The objective of this study is to examine the dynamic effects of currency devaluation with consideration to export and import of goods and services as well as consumer price index. In this case we restrict the coefficients of Labour (L) and capital (K) such that $\{\beta_1 = \beta_2 = 0\}$

$$\ln Y = \Omega_* + \beta_3 \ln R + \beta_4 \ln X + \beta_5 \ln M + \beta_6 \ln V \quad (4)$$

Where $\ln A = \Omega_*$

Introducing the time path, the econometric model is thus expressed as

$$\ln Y_t = \Omega_* + \beta_3 \ln R_t + \beta_4 \ln X_t + \beta_5 \ln M_t + \beta_6 \ln V_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (5)$$

In a more compact form, equation (5) may be expressed as

$$y_t = \Omega_* + w_t \beta + e_t \quad (6)$$

Where

y_t represents the dependent variables during the time t period

β represents a $k \times 1$ vector of slope parameters

Ω_* are the intercept terms

w_t represents the vector of independent variables which are integrated processes of order 1 in which case

$$w_t = w_{t-1} + e_t \quad (7)$$

Switching from static to dynamic model, the dynamic ordinary least square estimator employs lag and lead time by using past and future value of Δw_t in equation (6) as auxiliary regressors.

$$y_t = \Omega'_t + w'_t \beta_1 + \sum_{i=-p}^p \beta_i \ln \Delta w_{t+i} + \epsilon_t \quad (8)$$

Where

$$\epsilon_t = \epsilon_t + \sum_{j=1}^p \phi_j \epsilon_{t+j} \quad (9)$$

Table1: Description of Variables

Variable	Description	Acronym	Measurement
Dependent Variable			
Gross Domestic Product(GDP)	The sum of gross value added by all resident producers in the economy plus any product taxes and minus any subsidies not included in the value of the products.	GDP (Y)	Economic Growth
Independent Variables			
Exchange Rate (ER)	This is official exchange rate of Naira to US dollar measured in Naira per US dollar.	EXCR (R)	Currency Devaluation
Exchange Rate Returns (ERR)	Exchange Rate Returns	L β EXCR (L β R)	Logarithm of first difference of exchange rate
Export of goods and services (EXPT)	This is the value of all goods and other market services provided to the world in billions of Naira	EXPT (X)	Export Volume
Export of goods and services (IMPT)	This is the value of all goods and other market services provided to the world in billions of Naira	IMPT (M)	Import Volume
Consumer Price Index (CPI)	This is the index of consumer prices with a rise above 100 meaning an increase in prices and below 100 meaning a decrease in prices of goods and services. When it is equal to 100, it indicates stability in consumer prices.	CPI (V)	Inflation rate which is the rate of change in consumer price index
<i>Sources: Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, World Development Indicators (WDI) of the World Bank Group</i>			

Source: Author's Compilation

The Unit Root Test

The need to account for the stationarity condition of the data series for each of the variables in this study called for the unit root test. When a variable is stationary at level, it is said to be a stationary process and integrated of order zero, that is, **I(0)**. On the other hand, when a variable is stationary at first difference, it is said to be a non-stationary process and integrated of order 1, that is, **I(1)**. The study employed augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test. This test is based on the regression equation of the form

$$\Delta Q_t = \varphi_0 + \varphi_t + \Phi Q_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \Omega_i \Delta Q_{t-i} + u_t \tag{10}$$

Where

ΔQ_t are the first differences of the series Q_t , p represents the optimal lag order, u_t is the disturbance error term and the subscript t is the time path, φ_0 is the constant term, φ_t is the time trend, while $Q_t = [y_t, w_t]$ is the series concerned.

The ADF unit root test conventionally tests the null hypothesis of unit root (non-stationary) against the alternative hypothesis of no unit root (stationary), that is, [$H_0: \Phi = 0$] as against the one-sided alternative [$H_1: \Phi > 0$] in equation (9). We tested the ADF statistics against the 5% Mackinnon critical values to arrive at the conclusion on whether a variable is a stationary $I(0)$ or non-stationary $I(1)$. In addition to ADF (Dickey & Fuller, 1979), the study also adopted an alternative unit root test popularly known as KPSS (Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin, 1992) unit root test. In this case the null hypothesis of no unit root (stationary) is tested against the alternative hypothesis of unit root (non-stationary), that is, [$H_0: \rho > 0$] as against the one-sided alternative, [$H_1: \rho = 0$].

This is in order to have a check and balance on the order of integration of the data series used for this study.

Result and Discussion

Descriptive summary of variables

1: Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 presents the result of the descriptive analysis in tabular form. It shows the descriptive summary of the study variables in their original form as well as in their log-transformations. The descriptive statistics such as the mean, median, minimum, maximum, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis are given as shown in the table so also the outcome of log transformation of each of the variables in the analysis. All the variables are positively skewed and the skewness value for each of the dataset is greater than (+1), hence, the distribution is said to skew to the right. The kurtosis is a statistic used to measure the peakedness of a probability distribution of a random variable. The kurtosis of each of the variables except for export is said to be greater than the threshold of 3, hence, the dataset is said to have a heavier tails than a normal distribution, that is, they are more in tails than a normal distribution. The kurtosis value for each of the variables is greater than (+1), hence, the distribution of the data is said to be leptokurtic.

Table 2a: Descriptive Statistics of variables in level form

Variable	Descriptive Statistics						
	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis
GDP	34092.98	7515.812	171898.4	144.8312	46798.45	1.373405	3.828748
EXPT	6076.214	2335.789	22824.41	8.4256	7510.465	1.012531	2.588524
IMPT	5430.601	1406.406	32334.65	5.084	7967.721	1.886919	6.16181
EXCR	93.83175	97.0177	388.05	0.5467	98.35408	1.080578	3.761314
CPI	68.65971	32.3941	350.3	0.48936	85.31352	1.544195	4.85471

Source: Authors' Compilation

Table 2b: Descriptive Statistics of variables while in log transformation

Variable	Descriptive Statistics						
	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis
LGDP	8.706019	8.921369	12.05466	4.975569	2.398555	-0.23002	1.621447
LEXPT	6.965634	7.755103	10.03559	2.131275	2.613354	-0.53378	1.944693
LIMPT	6.601526	7.211111	10.38389	1.626098	2.792816	-0.45731	1.828036
LEXCR	3.380555	4.573729	5.961134	-0.60386	2.070039	-0.71787	2.168194
LCPI	2.954534	3.474245	5.85879	-0.71466	2.066028	-0.48245	1.849008

Source: Author’s compilation

2: Trend of Variables

The trend of the variables is graphically represented and/or shown in Figure 1. The growth rate of GDP was smoother than all the other variables, though they were all characteristically trended upward except for export and import that exhibit some swings in their growth path likewise the exchange rate.

Result of Unit Root Test

The results in Table 3 show that all variables in this study are found to be integrated of order one, that is they are all I(1). All of the variables therefore are said to be non-stationary. The dynamic OLS are said to produce a robust result when variables are integrated of order one and are found to be cointegrated.

Table 3: Result of the Unit Root Tests

Variables	ADF t-Stat	KPSS LM-Stat	Decision Rule
LGDP(constant only)	-1.0468	0.7613	I(1)
∅LGDP (constant only)	-3.2925	0.1965	
LGDP(constant with trend)	-0.1090	0.1573	
∅LGDP (constant with trend)	-3.4101	0.1429	
LEXPT (constant only)	-1.3405	0.7310	I(1)
∅LEXPT (constant only)	-10.6728	0.2001	
LEXPT (constant with trend)	-2.5812	0.1877	
∅LEXPT (constant with trend)	-10.4795	0.1020	
LIMPT (constant only)	-0.5146	0.7403	I(1)
∅LIMPT (constant only)	-5.4608	0.1456	
LIMPT (constant with trend)	-1.4245	0.1654	
∅LIMPT (constant with trend)	-5.4187	0.1312	
LCPI_NIG (constant only)	-1.2970	0.7485	I(1)
∅LCPI_NIG (constant only)	-3.6446	0.2667	
LCPI_NIG (constant with trend)	-1.1904	0.1794	
∅LCPI_NIG (constant with trend)	-3.7683	0.0972	
LEXCR (constant only)	-1.7809	0.7235	I(1)
∅LEXCR (constant only)	-5.3557	0.2766	
LEXCR (constant with trend)	-1.2962	0.1868	
∅LEXCR (constant with trend)	-5.5838	0.0598	

**L-Critical Values for ADF are [-3.6105, -2.9390, -2.6079] *∅-Critical Values for ADF are [-3.6156, -2.9411, -2.6091] at(1%, 5% and 10%)level of sig respectively *L-Critical Values for KPSS are [0.7390, 0.4630, 0.3470] *∅-Critical Values for KPSS are [0.7390, 0.4630, 0.3470] at(1%, 5% and 10%) level of sig respectively
**L-Critical Values for ADF are [-4.2119, -3.5298, -3.1964] **∅-Critical Values for ADF are [-4.2191, -3.5331, -3.1983] at (1%, 5% and 10%)level of sig respectively **L-Critical Values for KPSS are [0.216 0, 0.1460, 0.1190] **∅-Critical Values for KPSS are [0.2160, 0.1460, 0.1190] at (1%, 5% and 10%) level of sig respectively*

[*L-indicates with constant only and at level while *∅-indicates with constant only and at first difference]
[**L-indicates with constant only and at level while **∅-indicates with constant only and at first difference]

Johansen Multivariate Cointegration Test

In order to confirm if the group of non stationary time series converge to a long-run equilibrium, we adopted a multivariate cointegration test of Johansen which aside from confirming the existence of cointegration relationship also reveals the number of cointegrating vector. The result in Table 4 shows that the variables are cointegrated. From the table, there are three cointegrating vector which indicate a strong long-run relationship among the variables. The presence of cointegration provide an evidence that the variables converge to a long-run equilibrium.

Table 4: Result of Johansen Multivariate Cointegration Test

Johansen Maximum Likelihood (Trace test)	Null Hypothesis	Alternative Hypothesis	λ, γ	5% critical value
	r=0	∅	168.557*	69.819
	r 1	r=2	91.951*	47.856
	r 2	r=3	35.449*	29.797
	r 3	r=4	13.952	15.495
		r=5	2.837	3.841

Johansen Maximum Likelihood (Max-Eigenvalue test)	Null Hypothesis	Alternative Hypothesis	λ_1	5% critical value
	r=0	r=1	76.606*	33.877
	r=1	r=2	56.501*	27.584
	r=2	r=3	21.497*	21.132
	r=3	r=4	11.115	14.265
	r=4	r=5	2.837	3.841

Source: Authors' compilation

Hansen Cointegration result

Due to the fact that cointegration of our variables is a required condition that has to be met before we can proceed to the estimation technique designed for this study, we thought it necessary to have a double assurance of cointegration of our variables, hence, the use of alternative cointegration test developed by Hansen. The result of Hansen cointegration test result is presented in Table 5. The null hypothesis is that the series are cointegrated. Since this hypothesis cannot be rejected at 0.05 level, we draw conclusion that the series are cointegrated.

Table 5: Result of Hansen Cointegration Test

Null Hypothesis: Series are cointegrated				
Lc statistic	Stochastic Trends (m)	Deterministic Trends (k)	Excluded Trends (p2)	p-value
0.0386	4	0	0	<0.2

Source: Author's Compilation

The Dynamic Models

The first dynamic model used lead and lag time (1, 1), the second used lead and lag time (2, 2) while the third used lead and lag time (3, 1). It should be noted that at the end, the study finally adopted the model which yields the lowest possible long-run variance. The result of the dynamic model estimates is presented in Table 6. Table 6A presents the result of currency devaluation effect on economic growth while Table 6B presents the result of its associated returns. The three dynamic models show that currency devaluation as well as its associated returns has a contractionary effect on economic growth. Both currency devaluation and its associated returns have significant negative effect on economic growth with currency devaluation returns having greater effect. While the export trade has significantly positive effect, import trade has a significantly negative effect on economic growth. Also, the result from the table shows that inflation contributed positively and significantly to economic growth. However, we have some challenges with the result of model 1 while the result of model 3 appears to be more robust with that of model 2. Also, despite the associated high adjusted R-square, model 1 failed to meet up with the underlying assumption of absence of autocorrelation in the residuals of the models. Model 3 result as presented in Table 6(A and B) is finally adopted as the best since the residuals are normally

distributed, there is absence of autocorrelation in the residuals, and is also the model with the highest adjusted R-square and the lowest long-run variance relative to the first and second dynamic models. On the strength of this, the third dynamic model, as shown in the table, is the basis for policy recommendations. From the result, currency devaluation as well as its returns measured as log difference of naira-dollar exchange rate has a contractionary effect on economic growth. An increase in exchange rate of naira to dollar will reduce economic growth in line with the structuralist view on currency devaluation and economic growth nexus. The three variables used as control in this study have a significant effect on the entire model outcomes. For instance, while import volume has a significantly negative contribution, export volume and inflation have a significantly positive contribution. This result agrees with some empirical studies particularly Ribeiro et al., (2019) for sample of 54 developing countries, Özcan (2020) for Turkey, Cottani et al., (1990) for 24 cross-section of developing countries, Bahmani-Oskooee et al., (2002) for five Asian countries. However, the finding is in conflict with some other empirical studies who suggest an expansionary effect of currency devaluation on economic growth in line with classical economics. Such studies include Missioet. al., (2015), for 63 developing countries, Tarawalie (2010) for Sierra-Leone, Di Nino et al. (2011) for Italy, Chen (2012) for 28 provinces in China, Aman et al. (2013) for Pakistan, Obansa et. al (2013) for Nigeria, Habib et al. (2017) for a panel of 150 countries, mixed data sample, Narayan (2007) for Fiji countries, Rodrik (2008) for panel of 188 countries.

Table 6: Result of Dynamic OLS Estimates

IV	<i>Dependent Variable = lnGDP</i>								
	Model 1			Model 2			Model 3		
	Result of Dynamic OLS (DOLS) with lead and lag time (1,1) / (2,2) / with lead and lag time (3,1)								
	Coefficient	t-stat	P-value	Coefficient	t-stat	P-value	Coefficient	t-stat	P-value
<i>InEXPT/GDP</i>	1.0940	2.329	0.0205	1.2361	5.4595	0.000	1.1634	5.9506	0.0004*
<i>InIMPT/GDP</i>	-1.5835	-4.843	0.0001	-1.7983	-7.2917	0.000	-1.6148	-7.0144	0.0001*
<i>InCPI_NIG</i>	1.3328	9.266	0.0001	1.7308	15.4376	0.000	1.3715	14.8677	0.0001*
<i>InEXCR</i>	-1.0250	-0.429	0.6669	-0.3393	-0.7301	0.4611	-0.2185	-1.0383	0.3027**
<i>C</i>	2.4000	2.402	0.0165	5.2402	6.9338	0.000	3.2006	9.0690	0.0001*
<i>R-Square</i>	0.9956			0.9996			0.9996		
<i>Adj. R-squar</i>	0.9956			0.9985			0.9985		
<i>Long-run Variance</i>	0.0346			0.0027			0.0027		
Diagnostic tests	Residuals autocorrelation Test (Breusch-Godfrey = 7.0857(0.000)			Residuals autocorrelation Test (Breusch-Godfrey = 12.356(0.000)			Residuals autocorrelation Test (Breusch-Godfrey = 1.1716(0.55)		
	Residuals Normality Test (Breusch-Pagan = 12.833(0.000)			Residuals Normality Test (Breusch-Pagan = 2.1977(0.332)			Residuals Normality Test (Breusch-Pagan = 2.0666(0.225)		

Table 6b: Dynamic OLS Estimates with Currency Devaluation Returns*Dependent Variable = InGDP*

IV	Result of Dynamic OLS (DOLS) with lead and lag time (1, 1)			Result of Dynamic OLS (DOLS) with lead and lag time (2, 2)			Result of Dynamic OLS (DOLS) with lead and lag time (3, 3)		
	Coefficient	t-stat	P-value	Coefficient	t-stat	P-value	Coefficient	t-stat	P-value
<i>InEXPT/GDP</i>	0.0647	2.328	0.0205	0.2391	5.455	0.0002	1.2696	9.395	0.0000*
<i>InIMPT/GDP</i>	-1.6894	-2.843	0.0031	-1.7940	-2.494	0.0104	-2.0167	-11.160	0.0000*
<i>InCPI_NIG</i>	1.5378	8.206	0.0000	1.5238	15.438	0.0000	1.6054	14.145	0.0000*
<i>InEXCR</i>	0.0732	2.179	0.0389	0.2220	2.722	0.0011	0.2711	4.848	0.0000*
<i>C</i>	2.4052	4.422	0.0005	3.2439	6.954	0.0000	2.3532	4.893	0.0000*
<i>R-Square</i>	0.9976			0.9996			0.9997		
<i>Adj. R-squar</i>	0.9946			0.9984			0.9989		
<i>Long-run Variance</i>	0.046			0.007			0.008		
Diagnostic tests	Residuals autocorrelation Test (Ljung-Box) = 2.0065(0.006)			Residuals autocorrelation Test (Ljung-Box) = 0.3325(0.817)			Residuals autocorrelation Test (Ljung-Box) = 1.7716(0.555)		
	Residuals Normality Test (Jarque-Bera) = 1.0509(0.572)			Residuals Normality Test (Jarque-Bera) = 1.2103(0.302)			Residuals Normality Test (Jarque-Bera) = 2.9846(0.229)		

5. Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

The literature unfolds two key channels through which currency devaluation affects economic growth. One of these is export promotion drive by reducing prices of export in foreign countries such that makes export prices more competitive in foreign market and boost demand for export. Currency devaluation would increase the demand for export in the foreign market due to reduction in prices and hence create some output effects as theory suggests. The other channel is through import restriction such that reduces the domestic demand for imported goods due to a rise in import prices at home market, hence the need to switch over to consumption of locally produced goods. It is plausible indeed to anchor on the fact that an increase in import prices can have a lasting influence on consumer taste against imported goods and in favour of locally produced goods. These two channels provide justification for intensive research on differential output effect of currency devaluation across countries of the world. The increase in demand for export and reduction in import demand are believed to raise aggregate output through net export value in line with classical view. The increase in the prices of import raise the cost of production inputs and lowers the profits of firms leading to contraction of output. On the basis of these controversial views, this study examines the output effect of currency devaluation as well as its associated uncertainty exploring the Nigerian experience. Annual time series data were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin and World Development Indicators (WDIs) of the World Bank Group. The statistical properties of the variables as well as the issue of stationarity were dealt with in the preliminary analysis while the three models were estimated for each of currency devaluation and its associated uncertainty using dynamic ordinary least square (DOLS) estimation technique. The result shows that variables are said to be integrated of first order. Both Johansen and Hansen cointegration techniques reveals that the integrated variables are cointegrated. The DOLS result shows that currency devaluation and its associated returns among other variables have a significantly negative effect on output. This implies that as the

exchange rate of naira relative to US dollar increases, the aggregate output of the economy contracts, hence, both devaluated currency and its associated returns produces a contractionary effect on the aggregate economic output in line with the view of the structural economists. The study concludes by recommending a significant reduction in exchange rate of naira relative to US dollar, sharp reduction in import especially consumer goods as well as raising the export volume to generate a substantial economic growth in Nigeria.

References

- Acemoglu D, Robinson JA. 2006. Economic Origins of Dictatorship and Democracy. New York: Cambridge Univ.Press7(01), 195-197.
- Acharya, A (2010), Contractionary Devaluation in the Southern Cone: The case of Chile. *Journal of Development Economics*, 23, 135-151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2-18.07.022/>
- Adekoya, O. M. &Fagbohun, A. (2001).Currency Devaluation and Manufacturing Output Growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 6(7), 207-218.
- Agenor, P. and Montiel, P. (1996).Development Macroeconomics.Princeton University Press.
- Aman, Q., Ullah, I., Khan, M.I. and Khan, S. (2013). Linkages between Exchange Rate and Economic Growth in Pakistan, *European Journal of Law and Economics*.44(1), 157-164.
- Alexander Culiuc (2020). Real Exchange Rates Overshooting in Large Depreciations: Determinants and Consequences”. IMF Working Paper WP/20/60, International Monetary Fund, Washington DC.
- Bahmani-Oskooee, M., Chomsisengphet, S. and Kandil, M. (2002). Are Devaluations Contractionary in Asia.*Journal of Post Keynesian Economics*, 25(1), pp. 69-81.
- Carbaugh, R. J. (2009). International Economics, 12th edition, Cengage learning, Ohio.
- Chen, J. (2012). Real Exchange Rate and Economic Growth: Evidence from Chinese Provincial data. PSE Working Papers, 2012-05, 127.
- Cottani, J., Domingo, C. &Shahbaz, M. K. (1990). Real Exchange Rate Behaviour and Economic Performance in LDCs. *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, 39(1), 61-76.
- Çelik, T., Çelik B. & Barak, D. (2017).Real Exchange Rate and Economic Growth Relationship in Transition Economies.SuleymanDemirel University, *The Journal of Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences*, 22(3), pp. 877-890.
- Cooper, R. (1971). Currency devaluation in developing countries. Essays in international finance, No.86, Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press.
- Di Nino, V., Eichengreen, B. &Sbracia, M. (2011). Real Exchange Rates, Trade, and Growth: Italy 1861– 2011. Bancad'Italia Economic History Working Papers, No. 10.

- Edward, F., (1985). Can Church Education be Theological Education? *SAGE Journals*, 20(1), 42, 158-171 <https://doi.org/10.1177/004057368504200202>
- Kallianiotis, J. N. (2013). Exchange Rates and International Financial Economics: History, Theories, and Practices. Palgrave Macmillan, New York.
- Kamal P. Upadhyaya, (1999). Currency devaluation, aggregate output, and the long run: an empirical study. *Economics Letters*, 64(2), 197-202.
- Klein, M. W. & Shambaugh, J. C. (2010). Exchange Rate Regimes in the Modern Era. Massachusetts Institute of Technology
- Krugman, P. R., Obstfeld, M. & Melitz, M. J. (2012). International Economics Theory and Policy. 9th edition, Pearson Education, Inc., Boston
- Krugman, P. & Taylor, L., (1978). Contractionary effects of Devaluation. *Journal of international economics*, 8, 445-456.
- MacDonald, R. (2007). Exchange Rate Economics: Theories and Evidence, Routledge, New York,
- Missio, F.J., Jayme, G.F., Britto, G. & Oreiro, J.L. (2015). Real Exchange Rate and Economic Growth: New Empirical Evidence. *Metroeconomica*, 66(4), pp. 686-714.
- Mohammed, A. O., Agboola, H. Y., Moshood, K. A. & Abdullah, O. (2020). The Effects of Currency Devaluation on Output Growth in Developing Economies with Currency Crises. *Working Papers 7, Department of Economics, University of Ilorin*.
- Narayan, P.K. & Narayan, S., (2007). Is devaluation expansionary or contractionary? Empirical evidence from Fiji. *Applied Economics*, 39(20), 2589-2598.
- Obadan, M. I. (2006). Overview of Exchange Rate Management in Nigeria from 1986 to date. *An International Multi-Disciplinary Journal*, 30(3), 1-9.
- Obansa, S. A. J., Okoroafor, O. K. D., Aluko, O. O. & Millicent Eze (2013). Perceived Relationship between Exchange Rate, Interest Rate and Economic Growth in Nigeria: 1970-2010. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(3), pp. 116-124.
- Ozcan Karahan (2020). "Influence of Exchange Rate on the Economic Growth in the Turkish Economy. *Bandırma Onyediyül University, Faculty of Economics*. No. 1/2020, 21-<https://doi.org/10.5817/FAI2020-1-2>
- Radaelli, G. (1995). Exchange Rate Determination and Control. Routledge, New York.
- Ribeiro, R. S. M., McCombie, J. S. L. & Lima, G. T. (2019). Does Real Exchange Rate Undervaluation Really Promote Economic Growth? *Structural Change and Economic Dynamics*, 50, pp. 408-417.
- Rodrik, D. (2008). The Real Exchange Rate and Economic Growth. *Brookings Papers on Economic Activity*, 2, 365-412.
- Salvatore, D. (2006). International Economics, Shaums's Outline Series. 4th edition. Tata Mc-Graw-Hill, New Delhi
- Tarawalie, A. B. (2010). Real Exchange Rate Behaviour and Economic Growth: Evidence from Sierra Leone. *South African Journal of Economic and Management Sciences*, 13(1), 8-23.

Yiheyis, Z.(2006). The Effects of Devaluation on Aggregate Output: Empirical Evidence from Africa. *International Review of Applied Economics*, 20(1), 21-45.

Zelalem, F. C. (2006).Controlling the Informal Sector: Solid Waste Collection and the Addis Ababa City Administration 2003-2005.Master's thesis.